

OS Awards

European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source SW/HW Initiatives

D4.3 Awards Event Framework 1

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable, D4.3 Awards Event Framework 1, focuses on the necessary elements of the 2026 ceremony such as audience, speakers, format, topics and panels and agenda, among others.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/ Acronym	Definition
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EOA, EOSAcademy	European Open Source Academy
EOSAwards	European Open Source Awards
FOSDEM	Free Open Source Software Developers' European Meeting
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS	Member State

OS	Open Source
OFE	OpenForum Europe
OSWeek	Open Source Week
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
Trust-IT	Trust-IT Services
WP	Work Package

Legal Disclaimer

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About OS Awards.EU

OS Awards.EU is a 30-month initiative dedicated to establishing a European Open Source Academy and a prominent European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source Software (OS SW) and Hardware (HW). By creating the annual European Open Source Awards, guided by the expert European Open Source Academy, the project will celebrate outstanding contributions and foster greater interest, integration, utilisation, and exploitation of OS assets across Europe.

Strategically leveraging the EU Open Source Week alongside key European events, the project will amplify the awards’ profile and engage the community. The European OS Academy, in collaboration with the European Commission, will ensure award legitimacy and drive open source skills development. By intertwining recognition, legitimacy, and community engagement, OS Awards.EU aims to cultivate a comprehensive strategy that drives innovation, advances open source technologies, enhances EU competitiveness, and strengthens its open strategic autonomy.

OS Awards.eu Partners

The **OS Awards.eu** consortium consists of 7 partners from six different European countries:

1. RISE RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN AB (RISE), Sweden
2. OPENFORUM EUROPE (OFE), Belgium
3. FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION (TECNALIA), Spain
4. TRUST-IT SERVICES SRL (Trust-IT), Italy
5. BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION (BSC CNS), Spain
6. ASSOCIATION PROFESSIONNELLE EUROPEENNE DU LOGICIEL LIBRE (APELL asbl), Belgium
7. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN

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Executive Summary

The European Open Source Awards 2026 (EOSAwards 2026) Event Framework (formally titled, D4.3 Awards Event Framework 1) focuses on the necessary elements to produce the EOSAwards 2026 ceremony.

In the **Introduction section**, the key details of the event are provided. The European Open Source Awards 2026 will be held on 29 January 2026, 18:00 CET at the Bibliothèque Solvay, Leopoldpark, Rue Belliard 137, 1040 Brussels, Belgium. The event is by-invitation only and includes a reception, awards ceremony and networking dinner. Dress code is formal eveningwear with around 150 guests expected.

The **Event Management and Organisation section** outlines the structure of the event organisation which comprises of an Organising Committee which looks after the technical production of the event, and a Programme Committee which looks after the agenda provides strategic direction for the Organising Committee to execute. The section also includes an overview of the resources utilised.

A section is dedicated to the confirmed **Programme** to-date.

The **Technical Production section** forms the heart of this document which outlines the various organisational aspects of the event including venue, audio-visuals, catering, entertainment, design elements including branding and decorations, the laureate package, participation and guest relation, the communications plan and risk management.

The final section dedicated to **Evaluation and Reporting** describes the various mechanisms and processes in place to gather and report feedback and the outcomes of the EOSAwards 2026.

1 Introduction

This is the first Awards Event Framework which outlines the necessary elements of the 2026 Ceremony of the European Open Source Awards scheduled to be held on 29 January 2026 at the Bibliothèque Solvay in Brussels. This document will provide details regarding the audience, speakers, awardees, presenters, format, topics, agenda as well as other organisational details that will ensure the success and achievement of the goals of the event.

1.1 Event overview

The European Open Source Awards Ceremony 2026 is one of the flagship activities of the European Open Source Academy which is tasked with advancing public recognition of Open Source Software and Open Source Hardware in Europe. Through the annual awards ceremonies, the Academy celebrates and honours the exceptional contributions made to the open source community.

The ceremony aims to increase public recognition of Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware, and Open Technologies by strengthening awareness, understanding, appreciation, and support to experts' contributions across industry, in the public sector, everyday life, and beyond.

The main audience of the event is policymakers, European industry, the established open source ecosystem in Europe and beyond and, through media visibility, the general public.

Event name: European Open Source Awards 2026

Date & time: 29 January 2026, 18:00 CET

Venue: Bibliothèque Solvay, Leopoldpark, Rue Belliard 137, 1040 Brussels, Belgium

Event type and format: Reception, awards ceremony and networking dinner

Dress code: Formal eveningwear

Expected attendance: 150 (initially set at 170, but reduced due to venue restrictions)

Organiser: European Open Source Academy

1.2 Event goals

The desired goals of the event are drawn from several sources, chief of which, is the Awards Framework (OS Awards D4.2). It also takes cues set by the Constitution of the European Open Source Academy (OS Awards.EU D4.1) as well as the overarching objectives of the OS Awards project.

- Provide the main outlet for the recognising and celebrating individuals in Europe, or with strong European connections that have demonstrated long-term excellence and high-impact contributions to the global open source ecosystem. The focus is on individuals and their lifetime achievements through the entire annual series of ceremonies.
- Gather European policymakers, industry, media, and civil society at the event and showcase examples of open collaboration, innovation, and impact to them, focusing on concrete

examples of contributions and leadership from Europe in shaping European digital sovereignty, cybersecurity, competitiveness, and resilience.

- Raise awareness of open source and open technology through the use of media and popular communications, identifying concrete examples and case studies that can help demonstrate its impact and relevance to a wider audience of policymakers, industry, and the civil society.
- Through the annual ceremonies, project the European Open Source Academy as Europe's premier institution that recognises excellence in Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware and Open Technology.
- Demonstrate the awards as an example of how Europe values Open Source contributions.

2 Event Management and Organisation

To ensure a well-crafted programme delivered through a well-organised event, the management of the event rests on the establishment of two key bodies – the Programme Committee and the Organising Committee. Having two separate, but closely-liaising committees, each overseeing the two important aspects of the event, we ensure that sufficient time and effort is allotted to their development.

2.1 Programme Committee

The European Open Source Awards 2026 – Programme Committee decides on the content of the programme and the composition of the guest list. The programme committee will define the speakers, programme items and provide high-level guidance for the operational execution of the Organising Committee.

A member from the Organising Committee will liaise with the Programme Committee to ensure maximum alignment.

- Nicholas Gates (OFE), **Chair & Organising Committee Liaison**
- Lydia Pintscher (Wikimedia), EOSA Advocacy and Awareness Section Head
- Daniel Stenberg (Curl Project), EOSA President
- Amandine Le Pape (Element), EOSA Business & Impact Section Head
- David Cuartielles (Arduino), EOSA Skills and Education Section Head
- Astor Nummelin Carlberg (OFE)
- Sachiko Muto (RISE)
- Johan Linaker (RISE)

2.2 Organising Committee

The organising committee oversees and implements the technical production of the event based on the directions of the Programme Committee. Regular weekly meetings are organised to ensure the timely production of the event.

Role	Name
Chair	Rob Carrillo (Trust-IT)
Administration and Finance Coordinator	Rita Meneses (Trust-IT)
Logistics Coordinator	Marialetizia Mari (Trust-IT)
Communications Coordinator	Anja Radonjic (Trust-IT)
Programme Coordinator	Nicholas Gates (OFE)
Guest Relations Coordinator	Clara Thebert (OFE)

Technical/AV Manager	Marialetizia Mari (Trust-IT)
Committee Members	<p>Anna Eriksson (RISE), strategic advisor</p> <p>Christian Kummer (OFE), communications officer</p> <p>Matteo Zoppi (Trust-IT), videographer</p> <p>Ruben Tognetti (Trust-IT), photographer</p> <p>Lorenzo Calamai (Trust-IT), graphic designer</p> <p>Luca Di Fiore (Trust-IT), web developer</p>

2.3 Resources

The event will be implemented through the EU-funded project OS Awards.EU solely through a dedicated budget allocation for the event as well as the dissemination and communication allocation for the project.

The budget allocations will be used to fund the following: venue hire, catering, audio/visual services, decorations, awards medals and trophies, entertainment, printed and miscellaneous event materials.

A related cost to the event is the travel support offered to awardees, academy members and select members of the press.

Meanwhile, human resources assigned to the project will be the primary source of manpower particularly for the Programme and Organising Committees, videography and photography.

3 Programme

The programme outlined below was developed by the OS Awards 2026 Programme Committee. The following agenda items have been confirmed thus far as of 15 December 2025. The programme is expected to be refined with minor changes expected. Although the 2026 Laureates are named below, their identities will remain confidential until the actual announcement during the ceremony.

Time	Agenda Item
18:30-19:00	Reception
18:00-18:04	Opening Remarks <i>James Kanter, Host</i>
18:04-18:15	Welcome from the EOSA President <i>EOSA President Daniel Stenberg</i>
18:15-18:30	Fireside Chat <i>James Kanter, Host</i>
18:30-18:37	Presentation of Special Recognition for Business and Impact <i>Presented by Amandine Le Pape, EOSA Head of Section – Business & Impact Awarded to Frank Karlitschek (Nextcloud)</i>
18:37-18:44	Presentation of Special Recognition for Advocacy and Awareness <i>Presented by Lydia Pintscher, EOSA Head of Section - Advocacy & Awareness Awarded to Jenny Molloy (University of Cambridge, GOSH)</i>
18:44-18:51	Presentation of Special Recognition for Skills and Education <i>Presented by David Cuartielles, Head of Section - Skills & Education Awarded to Matt Venn (TinyTapeout)</i>
18:51-19:00	Presentation of Special Recognition for Community Impact <i>Awarded to Roberto Di Cosmo and Stefano Zacchiroli (Software Heritage)</i>
19:00-19:05	Musical Interlude
19:05-19:15	European Success Story: Blender <i>Blender COO Francesco Siddi</i>
19:15-19:40	Prize for Excellence in Open Source <i>Presented by EOSA President Daniel Stenberg</i>
19:40-19:45	Closing of the Ceremony <i>James Kanter, Host</i>
20:00	Dinner

4 Technical Production

4.1 Overview of requirements

A requirements overview is established from the beginning of the organisation activities to be able to ensure that decisions are fit for purpose for the requirements of the event.

	Requirements
Programme	1-1.5-hour ceremony programme. Maximum 3 concurrent speakers. Ability to show videos.
Audio and visuals (onsite)	Recording of the entire ceremony programme. AV services for the programme. AV services during entertainment.
Catering service	Welcome refreshments for the reception. Dinner for after the ceremony.
Communications	Pre-event promotional communications to generate anticipation within target audiences. Live event coverage via social media. Post-event communication to promote the awardees. Achieve wide visibility both within and outside the open source community.
Entertainment	Needs to lend dignity and complement the projected prestige of the event. Foreseen during the reception, a short intermission during the programme and during the networking dinner.
Guest relations	Compilation of a diverse guest list that ensures visibility of OS achievements both inside and outside the Open Source community. Dedicated outreach invitations for awardees, participants and the press. Provision of detailed information for confirmed attendees prior to the event.
Laureate package	Needs to be a material reflection of the recognition for open source. Laureates need to feel the special nature of the awards given out.
Venue	Capacity for at least 150 participants. Prestigious venue. Within Brussels.

4.2 Venue, Audio-Visuals, Catering and Entertainment

4.2.1 Venue

The venue selected for the event is the Bibliothèque Solvay situated at Leopoldpark, Rue Belliard 137, 1040 Brussels, Belgium which has spaces to host up to 250 guests. Aside from being able to provide all the logistical requirements needed by the ceremony such as the catering and audio-visual services, the main reason which led to its selection is its heritage of playing host to scientific luminaries, institutions and gatherings.

The Bibliothèque Solvay was founded by Ernest Solvay in 1902 to host the Institute of Sociology to scientifically analyse social issues – a first of its kind in Europe. It was the venue for his Solvay Conferences which gathered great scientific minds annually some of which include Nobel Prize Laureates such as Einstein and Bohr.

The event will be using the following spaces:

- Reading Room – Ceremony programme
- Mezzanine 1 and 2 – Reception and dinner

Figure 1 Bibliothèque Solvay - External View

Figure 2 Bibliothèque Solvay - Reading Room

Figure 3 Bibliothèque Solvay – Mezzanine

Figure 4 Bibliothèque Solvay - Rotunda and Seminar Room

Bibliothèque Solvay
Rez-de-chaussée

Figure 5 Bibliothèque Solvay Floor Plan - Ground Floor

Bibliothèque Solvay Étage

Figure 6 Bibliothèque Solvay Floor Plan – 1st Floor

Bibliothèque Solvay
Sous-sol

Figure 7 Bibliothèque Solvay Floor Plan – Ground Floor

4.2.2 Audio-Visuals

Audio and visual services will be provided by the venue. Given the requirements outlined in Section 5.1 Overview of Requirements, the following audio-visual services and equipment will be implemented.

Event Part	Event Space	Elements
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Reception	Entrance Hall and Mezzanines	Sound system for live string ensemble and recorded background music
Awards Ceremony	Reading Room	<p>General</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AV technical equipment and team • Sound system <p>Podium/stage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 85-inch screens • 3 microphones <p>Reading room (back part)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 comfort screens <p>Event recording</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 cameras • Recording system
Dinner	Entrance Hall and Mezzanines	Sound system for live string ensemble and recorded background music.

4.2.3 Catering service

Catering services, delivered via the Bibliothèque Solvay, are expected in two main parts of the event - the reception and the dinner. The ceremony itself will be a pause in the catering service to ensure maximum attention for the awarding.

While initial ideas were put forward for a seated gala format for the dinner, the Programme and Organising Committee opted to provide as much networking opportunities as possible to the attendees which led to the final choice of a standing format for the dinner.

Event Part	Catering Service
Reception	Welcome refreshments to be served to the guests after they check-in to the event as they mingle around the catering spaces.
Dinner	After the awards ceremony, the guests are led to the spaces reserved for the standing dinner where more substantial food and beverages are served.

4.2.4 Entertainment

During various parts of the event, a string ensemble, provided via the Bibliothèque Solvay, will be performing modern music arranged for strings to complement the event space surroundings and provide a touch of elegance to the event.

The string ensemble will be briefed to perform during the following:

- Reception – minimum 45 minutes.
- Ceremony – a 5-minute intermission.

- Dinner – 45+ minutes.

Where the string ensemble is not performing, background music will be played by the AV team.

4.3 Design elements

This section outlines the various design elements that will be part of the EOS Awards 2026.

4.3.1 Branding and decorations

As with the inaugural awards ceremony, the dedicated brand identity of the awards will be implemented.

Figure 8 European Open Source Awards Logo

The EOS Awards branding will be implemented on the event spaces used and the communications materials for the EOS Awards 2026.

Branded decorations for event spaces

Event Space	Branded decorations
External Spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Totem pole • Façade lighting (EOS Awards colours)
Entrance Hall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lectern for guest check-in: Logo on the lectern • Photo-wall, red carpet, crowd control dividers • EOS Academy flag • Signage for directions
Reading Room	<p>Overall space</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uplighters (in the EOS Awards colours) • Signage for directions <p>Stage (<i>Podium</i>)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Backwall • Lectern • Screen • EU flag • EOS Academy flag

Spaces for socials (Mezzanines)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roll-ups (at least two per space) • Signage for directions
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4.3.2 Laureate Package

As part of the EOS Awards 2026, the package received by awardees will be expanded. Aside from receiving a trophy and a diploma, a medal insignia will also be provided. The Laureate Package design inspiration, especially the trophy and medal were decided by the Programme Committee.

Trophy and Medal

The trophy for the 2026 awardees will be upgraded from a plexiglass and printed trophy based on the EOS Awards branding into a metallic and cast trophy designed and made especially for the EOS Awards.

A novel addition for all Laureates will be the medal insignia wearable by all award recipients from this ceremony onwards.

The design will not be based on the EOS Awards branding but will take inspiration from a modern and technological interpretation of “Yggdrasil”, a world-tree connecting all realms from Norse mythology. Just as Yggdrasil binds together gods, giants, elves, humans, and the dead—a shared infrastructure, so too do open-source projects serve varied ecosystems - distributed architecture, shared responsibility (Norns maintain the roots, Eagles guard the boughs, etc.) with open, interconnected nodes.

The symbolism to take inspiration from is a branching network/tree with many maintainers. It is gender-neutral, of European origin and the “tree” symbol has also been used frequently in an IT context.

Figure 9 EOS Awards Medal and Trophy Working Design

Diploma

A high-quality printed diploma bearing the name of the Laureate and the award, signed by the European Open Source Academy President and a citation highlighting the reason for their selection will be handed over to the Laureate.

4.4 Participation and Guest Relations

To ensure the achievement of the goals of the event, the Organising and Programme Committees have decided to continue its policy of making the event invite-only with an avenue for interested participants to express interest to attend the event. This ensures that OS Awards.EU and EOSA can ensure a curated guest list and that the capacity can be maximised by having the most influential and relevant guests present.

The guest list has been compiled comprising the following profiles:

- Civil Society
- Consortium
- European Commission
- Members of the European Parliament
- Experts
- Industry
- Media
- Member States Representatives, Permanent Representatives/Diplomats
- Open Source community representatives
- Research and Academia

Aside from the above guests, the guest list also include Laureates and EOSA members and their guests, and consortium members.

To-date, around 300 individuals have been invited to attend with already 1/3 of the maximum capacity already confirming within the first 2 weeks of the invitations being sent.

The following is a working timeline on the communication towards the guests:

- 1 Oct – 21 Nov 2025: Guest list compiled and curated.
- 24 Nov – 6 Dec 2025: Invitations sent out with deadlines to respond before the end of the year.
- Week of 7 Jan 2026: Follow-up to
 - Confirmed participants with form on privacy policy and photography and videography consent, and dietary restrictions
 - Confirmed press and media for any interview requests during the event, travel support etc.
- 26-28 Jan 2026: Reminders and follow-up confirmation on attendance.

4.5 Communication Plan

The Communication Plan for the EOSAwards 2026 is coordinated by the OS Awards.EU communications team led by Trust-IT with input from the Programme Committee spearheaded by OFE and contributions from all partners of the OS Awards.EU project.

Phase	Channel	Activity
Pre-event	EOSA Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOSA Website • EOSA Social Media • EOSA Magazine 	<u>October 2025</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of the Open Call for EOSAwards 2026 Nominations • Launch of the Open Call for EOSA Magazine 1st Issue contributions <u>November 2025</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closure of the two open calls for the EOSAwards 2026 nominations and EOSA Magazine 1st Issue contributions • Event listing published on the EOSA Website <u>December 2025-January 2026</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple weekly social media updates and promotional posts.
	EOSAwards Landing Page	Expansion of the EOSAwards landing page into a mini-site with the following new content sections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awards and Laureates • Nomination • Ceremony • Gallery • Past Editions
	Press and Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production and distribution of a pre-event press release announcing the upcoming EOSAwards 2026 in early January 2026. • Production and distribution of a general interest article referencing the EOSAwards 2026. • Production and preparation of the distribution list for the post-event press release.
Live	EOSA Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOSA Website • EOSA Social Media • EOSA Magazine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Footage shooting for the post-event video • Footage shooting for interview videos. • Distribution of the EOSA Magazine 1st Issue printed version • Launch of the EOSA Magazine 1st Issue digital edition • Live social media posting

	EOS Awards Mini-site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Go-live/unveiling of the Laureates directly after the 2026 Ceremony including profiles and initiatives.
	Press and media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordination and support for the on-site press and media in attendance. Distribution of the post-event press release announcing the Laurates of the EOS Awards 2026 with selected photos (embargoed for 29 January 2026, 22:00 CET and distributed only at that time).
Post-event	EOSA Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSA Website EOSA Social Media EOSA Magazine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication of the post-event press release as news. Monitoring and tracking communications impact.
	EOS Awards Mini-site and multimedia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication of the photo-gallery Updating the ceremony programme to include Laureates Publication of the post-event video and interviews/testimonials Publication of the ceremony recording
	Press and Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Follow-up press release uptake by the distribution list and compilation of press clippings and impact monitoring.

4.5.1 Hashtags

To mobilise multipliers of visibility and leverage audience-generated content across social media platforms, an official hashtag will be set that will be used across relevant EOSA channels:

#EOSAwards26

Guests present will be encouraged to post using the hashtag in their own social media feed thus expanding the visibility of the EOS Awards 2026.

4.5.2 Privacy and consent handling for photos and videos

The event will respect the privacy preferences of the guests. To accommodate for the guests that do not wish their photographs to be published in the public album, they may indicate this to the Organising Committee in the form that will be circulated to all confirmed guests before the event.

Guests that have expressed their preference not to be published online will be given a magnetic lapel pin that allows them to be easily recognised by the photographers during post-production. Their photographs will be excluded from the public album.

4.6 Risk Management

The following risks have been compiled from the previous experience in the EOS Awards 2025 as well as past experience in organising similar events by the Organising and Programme Committees with priority levels, likelihood and mitigation measures.

Risk, Likelihood and Priority Level	Mitigation Measures Implemented
Lack of media attendance or visibility <i>Likelihood: High</i> <i>Priority: High</i>	Scout and invite media both within and outside Belgium. Offer travel support to priority media. Also target new/non-traditional media such as influencers (YouTube, LinkedIn), podcasters etc. Also consider micro-influencers that have a dedicated following in specific relevant niches. Engage publicity specialists to support awareness raising.
Lack of engaging speeches during the programme <i>Likelihood: High</i> <i>Priority: Medium</i>	Programme Committee members will have a dedicated briefing session with each speaker in the programme, rehearsing and suggesting improvements in their parts.
Lack of attendees and diversity <i>Likelihood: Medium</i> <i>Priority: High</i>	Emphasise the exclusivity of the event and projecting it as a high-value event not to be missed if invited. Earlier compilation of the guest list. Increase communications and promotional activities prior to the ceremony to also build up the waiting list. In curating the guest list, seek for a balance between OS and non-OS participation.
Lack of adequate time for on-site event set-up <i>Likelihood: Low</i> <i>Priority: Medium</i>	Set-up of the venue is scheduled for the morning of 29 January 2026 from 8:00 CET. As most of the Organising Committee will not be involved in the EOSA General Assembly, they will have up to 4 hours to set-up the venue with several hours break before allowing consortium members to return to their accommodations and prepare and come back in time for the reception.
Unbalanced staff allocation and workload in various event aspects <i>Likelihood: Low</i> <i>Priority: Medium</i>	Plan staff allocations by setting up a Project Management and Operations tracker, taking staffing into account in the Run-of-Show and introducing a Staff Allocation Plan for 2026.
Unforeseen accidents	Insurance coverage policy has been secured for the event.

Likelihood: Low

Priority: Medium

5 Evaluation & Reporting

Evaluation and reporting for the EOS Awards 2026 will be carried out through the following:

- **Post-Event Survey:** A post-event survey form will be distributed to the guestlist the next day after the event with a deadline to respond within one week (*Responsible: Trust-IT*)
- **In-person feedback collection from attendees, academy members, awardees, staff:** Consortium members will be asked to gather feedback on-site informally from the attendees to gather firsthand face-to-face feedback on the event to be compiled and reported at the next immediate Technical Coordination meeting. (*Responsible: all OS Awards.EU consortium members*)
- **Post-Event Report:** A post-event report will be compiled based on the outcomes of the post-event survey, the in-person feedback collection, as well as the reports of the organising committee. It will be submitted as a deliverable, D4.4 Post-event report: Awards Event 1 in February 2026. (*Responsible: Trust-IT*)

6 Conclusion

The EOS Awards 2026 Event Framework provides a snapshot of the organisational aspects of the upcoming EOS Awards 2026 outlining the goals, the event management structure and production team, resources, various aspects of the event’s technical production, risk management and mitigation, and evaluation and reporting processes.

The following deliverable, D4.4 Post-event report: Awards Event 1, due in February 2026, will report on the main outcomes as well as lessons learned that will be useful for the next edition of the EOS Awards in 2027.